

Technical Report: Secure Image Capture and Monitoring Script

Marco Righi
Clinical Physiology Institute
National Research Council of Italy (CNR)
Via Aurelia Sud 54100 Massa, Italy
`marco.righi@cnr.it`

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Abstract

This report describes a Bash script designed for secure image capture and monitoring using a webcam. The script includes features for motion detection, image processing, and automated cleanup of old files. This document provides an overview of the script's functionality, configuration, and usage.

Keywords: Image Capture, Motion Detection, Bash Script, Webcam Monitoring, Image Processing, Automated Cleanup, Simple Surveillance, Secure Image Storage

1 Introduction

The Secure Image Capture and Monitoring Script is a tool developed to automate the process of capturing images from a webcam, detecting motion, and managing the storage of captured images. The script is written in Bash and leverages tools such as `fswebcam`, `ImageMagick`, and `bc`.

This software is available at <https://github.com/marcorighi/personalsecurewebcam>.

2 Description

This script stands out for its simplicity and ease of use. Unlike more complex systems such as Shinobi, ZoneMinder, and MotionEye, this script requires minimal setup and configuration, making it accessible even to users with limited technical expertise. The primary focus is on providing a straightforward solution for secure image capture and motion detection without the need for extensive hardware or software resources.

3 Comparison with Other Software

3.1 Shinobi

Shinobi is a powerful, open-source video management software written in Node.js. It supports a wide range of IP and USB cameras and offers advanced features such as real-time data streaming and multi-camera synchronization. However, its complexity and resource requirements can be a barrier for users seeking a simple solution [2].

3.2 ZoneMinder

ZoneMinder is a full-featured, open-source video surveillance software system. It supports a vast array of cameras and offers extensive customization options. While it is highly scalable and feature-rich, ZoneMinder can be challenging to install and configure, especially for users without a strong technical background [3].

3.3 MotionEye

MotionEye is a web frontend for the motion daemon, written in Python. It provides a user-friendly interface for setting up and managing video surveillance systems. MotionEye is easier to use compared to Shinobi and ZoneMinder, but it still requires a certain level of technical knowledge to install and configure [1].

4 Configuration

The script includes several configurable parameters:

- `OUTPUT_DIR`: Directory where captured images are stored.
- `LOG_FILE`: Path to the log file for recording script activities.
- `FRAME_DELAY`: Time delay between capturing frames.
- `FILE_RETENTION_DAYS`: Number of days to retain captured images before deletion.
- `IMAGE_FORMAT`: Format of the captured images (e.g., jpg).
- `RESOLUTION`: Resolution of the captured images.
- `FUZZY_VALUE`: Tolerance level for image comparison.
- `LOW_THRESHOLD`: Threshold for low variation detection.
- `LOW_THRESHOLD_ACTIVATION`: Activation threshold for low variation.
- `VARIATION_AVERAGE_THRESHOLD`: Percentage threshold on variation to start recording.
- `LOW_VARIATION_AVERAGE_THRESHOLD`: Threshold for low average variation.
- `VARIATION_HISTORY_SIZE`: Size of the variation history buffer.
- `SECONDS_BETWEEN_IMAGES_CLEANUP_CHECK`: Interval between cleanup checks.

5 Setup

The script performs the following setup steps:

- Creates necessary directories and log files.
- Defines functions for logging and capturing frames using `fswebcam`.

6 Temporary Files

The script creates temporary files for storing the current and previous images, as well as their processed versions:

```
IMAGE_prev=$(mktemp --suffix=.$IMAGE_FORMAT)
IMAGE_now=$(mktemp --suffix=.$IMAGE_FORMAT)
IMAGE_prev_processed=$(mktemp --suffix=.$IMAGE_FORMAT)
IMAGE_now_processed=$(mktemp --suffix=.$IMAGE_FORMAT)
```

7 Cleanup Mechanism

The script periodically deletes old images based on the specified retention period:

```
delete_old_files() {
    local current_time=$(date +%s)
    if (( current_time - last_cleanup_time >=
        ↪$SECONDS_BETWEEN_IMAGES_CLEANUP_CHECK )); then
        deleted_files=$(find "$OUTPUT_DIR" -type f -name "
            ↪*.$IMAGE_FORMAT" -mtime +"$FILE_RETENTION_DAYS
            ↪" -print -exec rm -f {} \;)
        if [ -n "$deleted_files" ]; then
            log "Deleted files: - $deleted_files"
        else
            log "No files deleted during cleanup."
        fi
        last_cleanup_time=$current_time
    fi
}
```

8 Dependency Check

The script verifies the presence of required commands:

```
for cmd in fswebcam compare magick bc; do
    if ! command -v "$cmd" >/dev/null 2>&1; then
        log "Error: -command-$cmd-not-found"
        exit 1
    fi
done
```

9 Motion Detection

The script captures the initial frame and logs the configuration. It then continuously captures frames and processes them to detect motion. The script uses ImageMagick to process and compare images, maintains a buffer of recent variations to calculate average variation, and starts and stops capturing based on the calculated variation and predefined thresholds.

10 Logging

The script logs significant events, such as the start and stop of image capture, errors, and cleanup activities:

```
log() {
    local message="$*"
    local timestamp
    timestamp=$(date +"%Y-%m-%d-%H:%M:%S")
    echo "[$timestamp]-$message" | tee -a "$LOG_FILE"
}
```

11 Signal Handling

The script handles termination signals to ensure proper cleanup of temporary files:

```
trap 'log -"Script termination ..."; -rm -f -"$IMAGE_prev" -"
    ↪$IMAGE_now" -"$IMAGE_prev_processed" -"
    ↪$IMAGE_now_processed"; -exit -0' SIGINT SIGTERM EXIT
```

12 Usage

To use the script, follow these steps:

1. Clone the repository:

```
git clone git@github.com:marcorighi/  
↪personalsecurewebcam.git  
cd personalsecurewebcam
```

2. Make the script executable:

```
chmod +x secure_get_image.sh
```

3. Run the script:

```
./secure_get_image.sh
```

13 Dependencies

Ensure the following commands are installed on your system:

- `fswebcam`
- `compare` (part of ImageMagick)
- `magick` (part of ImageMagick)
- `bc`

14 License

This project is licensed under the MIT License - see the `LICENSE` file for details.

15 References

References

- [1] motioneye. <https://github.com/motioneye-project/motioneye>. Accessed: 2025-01-17.
- [2] Shinobi. <https://shinobi.video/>. Accessed: 2025-01-17.
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